

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF ACUTE ZOTILJAM IN CHILDREN OF
ADOLESCENT AGE

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Abstract. *Pneumonia is a cold, a lung infection — inflammation of the lung tissue, usually caused by an infection, mainly with damage to the alveoli (development of inflammatory exudation in them).*

The term "pneumonia" unites a large group of diseases, each of which has characteristic differences in its etiology, pathogenesis, clinical picture, radiological signs, laboratory studies and treatment features.

Key words: *Classification, Distribution, Pathogenesis, Clinical picture*

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОСТРОГО ЗОТИЛЬЯМА У ДЕТЕЙ ПОДРОСТКОВОГО
ВОЗРАСТА.

Аннотация. *Пневмония — простуда, инфекция легких — воспаление легочной ткани, обычно вызванное инфекцией, преимущественно с поражением альвеол (развитием в них воспалительной экссудации).*

Термин «пневмония» объединяет большую группу заболеваний, каждое из которых имеет характерные различия по этиологии, патогенезу, клинической картине, рентгенологическим признакам, лабораторным исследованиям и особенностям лечения.

Ключевые слова: *Классификация, Распространение, Патогенез, Клиническая картина.*

Non-infectious inflammatory processes in the lung tissue are usually called pneumonitis or alveolitis in the case of primary damage to the respiratory parts of the lungs. Bacterial, viral-bacterial or fungal pneumonia often develops against the background of such aseptic inflammatory processes.

Tuberculosis kills 15 percent of children under 5 worldwide [source]. According to statistics, 808,694 children under the age of 5 died of pneumonia in 2017. It is noted that every 64 people who get this dangerous disease die. Due to pneumonia, dangerous complications occur in various organs of the patient.

According to the criteria of spread of the process, pneumonia can be classified as follows:

Focal (focal) — a small part of the lungs is damaged (bronchopneumonia — respiratory departments + bronchi);

Segmental — spreads to one or more segments of the lung;

Lobar — affects the lobe of the lung. A classic example of lobar pneumonia — croupous pneumonia — mainly inflammation of the alveoli and the adjacent pleura;

Converging - the merging of small foci and the expansion of the area of damage;

Total — if spread throughout the lungs.

In addition, pneumonia can be unilateral if it affects only one lung or bilateral if it affects both.

Depending on the cause, the following are distinguished:

Primary pneumonia develops as an independent disease;

Secondary pneumonia — develops against the background of another disease, for example, against the background of chronic bronchitis;

Radiation form - occurs against the background of x-ray treatment of oncological pathologies;

The post-traumatic form occurs as a result of injuries to the chest, as a result of which bronchial secretions are blocked and lung ventilation is disturbed, which leads to inflammatory processes in the lung tissue.

Depending on the origin, pneumonia is divided into the following forms.

Infectious - develops under the influence of pneumococcus, klebsiella, staphylococcus, streptococcus and other bacteria;

It has a viral genesis — most often, the herpetic form occurs in Epstein-Barr virus or cytomegalovirus infection;

It has a fungal genesis - the causative agent of the disease can be molds (*Aspergillus*, *Mucor*), yeast (*Candida*), endemic dimorphic fungi (*Blastomyces*, *Coccidioides*, *Histoplasma*), pneumocystis (*Pneumocystis*);

Mixed type — caused by two or more types of pathogens at the same time.

According to the nature of the process, the following are distinguished:

Acute pneumonia: in turn, it is divided into quick (up to 3 weeks) and long (up to 2 months) transient types;

Subacute pneumonia: clinical duration — about 3-6 weeks;

Chronic pneumonia (currently excluded from classifications): characterized by weak intensity and long duration — from several months to many years and decades.

Pathogenesis of pneumonia

The most common way for microorganisms to enter the lung tissue is the bronchogenic route, which includes aspiration, inhalation of microbes from the environment, the transfer of pathogenic flora from the upper respiratory tract (nose, larynx) to the lower part. passage, medical procedures - bronchoscopy, tracheal intubation, artificial ventilation of the lungs, treatment with inhaled drugs, etc.

The spread of infection by hematogenous route (blood) is less common, mainly in intrauterine infection of the fetus, septic processes and intravenous drug administration. Lymphogenic infection is reported in very rare cases.

After infection, the infectious agent settles in the epithelium of the respiratory bronchioles and begins to multiply, resulting in the development of acute bronchitis or bronchiolitis in various forms (from mild catarrhal form to necrotic form). The spread of microorganisms outside the bronchioles leads to inflammation of lung tissue or pneumonia. Foci of atelectasis appear due to violation of bronchial permeability. With the help of coughing and sneezing reflexes, the body tries to restore bronchial permeability, but as a result, the infection spreads to healthy tissues and new foci of pneumonia appear.

As a result of the disease, oxygen deficiency, shortness of breath, and in severe cases, heart failure may occur. Most often, segments II, VI, X of the right lung and VI, VIII, IX, X of the left lung are affected. Local lymph nodes - bronchopulmonary, paratracheal, bifurcation nodes are also involved in this process.

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